

Reaction of selected breeding lines to the black bug,^a Palawan, Philippines in 1984 dry season.

Breeding line ^b	Black bugs (no./hill) 20 DAI	Plant damage at indicated DAI		
		20	40	60
IR13149-71-3-2	149 abc	3.5 a	4.0 a	5.0 a
IR10781-75-3-2-2	133 ab	4.0 b	4.0 a	5.5 a
IR18350-175-2-3	155 abc	3.5 a	5.5 ab	7.5 ab
BG379-1	200 c	3.5 a	5.5 ab	8.0 b
IR19661-23-3-2-2	126 ab	5.0 bc	5.5 ab	8.0 b
IR12721-24-3-1	173 bc	5.0 bc	6.5 abcd	8.0 b
BW295-4	129 ab	4.5 bc	7.5 cdef	8.0 b
BR316-15-4-4-1	131 ab	5.5 bcd	6.0 abc	8.5 b
BR445-60-1b	162 bc	5.0 bc	7.0 bcdef	8.5 b
IR13240-108-2-2-3	134 ab	6.0 c	7.0 bcdef	8.5 b
IR25774-3-1-1	169 bc	4.5 bc	7.0 bcdef	8.5 b
IR36 (check)	167 bc	5.5 bcd	7.0 bcdef	8.5 b
Tjeremas (purple base)	109 ab	7.0 d	8.0 def	8.5 b
BG400-1	134 ab	5.5 bcd	8.5 g	9.0 c
B2791b-Mr-257-3-2	145 abc	4.5 bc	6.5 abcd	9.0 c
B3981c-Pn-200-2-2	97 a	7.0 d	8.5 g	9.0 c
Cul. 6914	170 bc	5.0 bc	8.5 g	9.0 c
IR12979-24-1	133 ab	5.5 bcd	7.0 bcdef	9.0 c
IR13415-9-3	161 bc	5.0 bc	7.0 bcdef	9.0 c
C1754-5	121 ab	5.5 bcd	7.5 cdef	9.0 c
IR31917-31-3-2	148 abc	5.5 bcd	8.0 def	9.0 c
Tjeremas (green base - local check)	203 c	5.0 bc	7.5 cdef	9.0 c

^a Av of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. ^b Breeding lines selected from the 300 test entries screened in Jul-Dec 1983.

The first 5 test entries tolerated high black bug population at 40 DAI (see table). However, IR13149-71-3-2 and IR10781-75-3-2-2 were the only entries that survived to 60 DAI. IR10781-75-3-2-2, which matures in 131 d, yielded 7 t/ha in 1980 dry season, is resistant to brown planthopper biotypes 1 and 3, and moderately resistant to green leafhopper. The two most resistant lines are being tested for yield under black bug infestation in Palawan. □

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Evaluation of germplasm accessions for green leafhopper (GLH) resistance

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From the IRRI germplasm collection, 204 GLH accessions with resistance to GLH *Nephotettix virescens*, brown planthopper, whitebacked planthopper, or leafhopper were evaluated for resistance to *N. nigropictus* (Stål) and *N. virescens* (Distant). Separate 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes for each GLH species were used with IR29 as the resistant check and Nira as the susceptible check. Seven days after sowing, seedlings were thinned to 15-20 per entry and infested with 4-5 3d-instar nymphs per seedling. When Nira seedlings died, entries were rated for damage using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale.

Sixty-five entries scored 0-5 for *N. nigropictus* and 105 for *N. virescens*. The entries were further evaluated in three replications. Susceptible entries (scores 6-9) were rejected.

Reactions to both GLH species were similar for many varieties. Fifty-one (25%)

Damage ratings of rice cultivars in seedbox screening for resistance to *N. nigropictus* and *N. virescens*, IRRI, 1983-84.

Cultivar	IRRI accession number	Origin	Damage rating ^a (grade 0-9)	
			<i>N. nigropictus</i>	<i>N. virescens</i>
Resistant to <i>N. nigropictus</i> and <i>N. virescens</i>				
Ari	25830	Bangladesh	3.7	2.4
Ashni	25831	Bangladesh	3.7	2.3
Aus Jhari	25833	Bangladesh	3.7	3.0
Bathuri	25838	Bangladesh	3.7	3.7
Chamka	25844	Bangladesh	3.0	3.7
Chiknal	25848	Bangladesh	3.0	3.0
Dhalashaita	25851	Bangladesh	2.3	3.0
Garia	25854	Bangladesh	1.3	2.3
Gungur Murali	25858	Bangladesh	3.0	3.0
Hasha	25861	Bangladesh	3.7	2.3
Hijolee	25862	Bangladesh	1.0	2.3
Pankhiraj	25911	Bangladesh	3.7	1.7
Terabali	25926	Bangladesh	3.7	1.7
Pahari Balam	31904	Bangladesh	3.0	3.7
D 59-6	33045	Bangladesh	3.0	3.0
Lalmoti	37522	Bangladesh	3.7	1.7
Kalimekri 77-5	37649	Bangladesh	3.7	3.0
Bow Pagal	43796	Bangladesh	3.0	3.0
Chakulia	43798	Bangladesh	3.7	3.0
Molica	43925	Bangladesh	3.0	3.0
Hnanwa Phingauk	4142	Burma	3.7	3.7
ASD7	6303	India	3.7	2.3
Shatika	35150	India	3.7	3.0
ARC14960	43034	India	3.0	3.0
Hassan Tareme	32311	Iran	3.7	3.0
Gadur	16246	Nepal	3.7	3.0
IR2034-289-1-1-1	32684	Philippines	3.7	3.0
Sulai	8908	Sri Lanka	1.7	1.7
Chianung Sen 11	26955	Taiwan	3.0	3.0

Cont'd

Cultivar	IRRI accession number	Origin	Damage rating ^a (grade 0-9)	
			<i>N. nigropictus</i>	<i>N. virescens</i>
<i>Moderately resistant to N. nigropictus and N. virescens</i>				
Gauk	33072	Bangladesh	5.0	5.0
Chini Atap	37403	Bangladesh	5.0	5.0
BR3	38625	Bangladesh	5.0	5.0
Dharia Bogi	43814	Bangladesh	5.0	5.0
Hanpa (Black)	43851	Bangladesh	5.0	4.0
Maguria	43921	Bangladesh	5.0	5.0
Sxc 108	35172	India	4.3	4.3
Amla	44932	India	5.0	5.7
I.B. Rose/Latisail	45848	India	5.0	5.0
Karpursail	46050	India	5.0	5.0
Rupsail	46586	India	5.0	5.0
Sachi	46612	India	5.0	5.0
Sadlaghu	46625	India	5.0	5.0
Intan	4230	Indonesia	5.0	5.0
Mas	5334	Indonesia	5.0	5.0
Dikwee	7814	Nigeria	4.3	5.0
<i>Resistant to N. virescens and susceptible to N. nigropictus</i>				
Chungur bali	25855	Bangladesh	6.3	3.0
Muijuri	25907	Bangladesh	7.0	1.7
Sona Biron	31633	Bangladesh	9.0	1.7
Lal Aswina	31670	Bangladesh	9.0	1.7
Molladiga	31675	Bangladesh	9.0	3.7
Kala Aman 961	32908	Bangladesh	7.0	3.7
Ellai	37424	Bangladesh	7.0	3.0
Lal paika	37523	Bangladesh	7.0	3.0
Laki 146	37709	Bangladesh	7.0	1.7
Dudhswar 15-146	37956	Bangladesh	7.0	1.7
Jessobalam 3-23	38009	Bangladesh	7.0	3.7
Latisail 11-122	38082	Bangladesh	9.0	3.0
Dhalgora	43813	Bangladesh	6.3	3.0
Ta-Poo-Cho z	4285	China	7.0	3.0
Ptb 20	5920	India	7.0	3.7
Katki	46091	India	7.0	3.0
Ratrio	28181	Pakistan	7.0	3.0
Milagrosa Mutant	26967	Philippines	7.0	3.7
IR5853-135-3-P3	39425	Philippines	7.0	3.0
IR5865-32-3	39434	Philippines	7.0	3.7
IR5896-10-2	39441	Philippines	7.0	3.0
<i>Resistant to N. nigropictus and susceptible to N. virescens</i>				
Najirsail	37237	Bangladesh	9.0	3.0
Peta	35	India	7.0	3.7
CO13	4897	India	9.0	3.7
ARC12176	41016	India	7.0	3.0
ARC14664	41672	India	7.0	3.0
Jessoa	45893	India	7.0	3.0
Katalgaria	46075	India	7.0	3.0
Bir-Co-Se-Mau 7	4349	China	6.3	3.7
IR2003-P7-7-4-2	32671	Philippines	9.0	3.7
IR2031-238-5-2-6-2	32680	Philippines	7.0	3.0
IR2070-464-1-3-6	32701	Philippines	9.0	3.7
IR42	36959	Philippines	7.0	3.7
Kosattawee	8927	Sri Lanka	6.3	3.7
Sir	Muragan36279	Sri Lanka	9.0	3.0

^a 0 = highly resistant, 9 = susceptible.

were resistant (grades 1-3), 99 (48.5%) moderately resistant (grades 3.1-5), and 54 (26.5%) susceptible to *N. nigropictus* (scores 5.1-7); and 96 (47.1%) resistant, 38 (18.6%) moderately resistant, and 70 (34.3%) susceptible to *N. virescens* (see table). Twenty-nine cultivars were resistant to both species, 21 were resistant to *N. virescens* but susceptible to *N. nigropictus*, and 14 were resistant to *N. nigropictus* but susceptible to *N. virescens*. Accessions resistant to both leafhopper species should be considered for use as donors in the breeding program for GLH resistance. □

Screening for resistance of IR varieties to green leafhoppers (GLH)

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Several rices have been identified and incorporated in breeding programs in Asia for *Nephotettix virescens* resistance. Twenty-seven modern (IR5-IR62) rices with moderate to high levels of *N. virescens* resistance have been released.

We evaluated IRRI varieties IR5 to IR60 for resistance to *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus*, another common rice green leafhopper, in a seedbox screening test. Separate seedboxes were used for each hopper species. Seeds were sown in rows in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes with Nira as the susceptible check. At 7 d after sowing seedlings were thinned to 15-20, entry and each was infested with 4-5 3d-instar nymphs of *N. nigropictus* or *N. virescens*. When the susceptible check died, test entries were rated for damage by the 1980 *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) 0-9 scale. Treatments were arranged in a complete randomized design with three replications.

Although the IR varieties were not bred for *N. nigropictus* resistance, levels of resistance were generally higher than

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